

Maybank Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the development of research around Maybank Sharia and Conventional. The research was conducted from 2013 to 2022, by searching national journals indexed by Sinta via the Garuda website, with the keyword " Maybank ". Based on the search results, there were 47 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a Library Research study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to Maybank is divided into 7 clusters and 139 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a Library Research study, there are 6 main themes related to Maybank Sharia and Conventional.

Keywords : Maybank Sharia and Conventional; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research

A. Introduction

The private bank Maybank Indonesia, belonging to the Malayan Banking Berhad (Maybank) group, is located in Indonesia. PT Internasional Indonesia (BII), which was founded in 1959, was the previous name of Maybank Indonesia. In 1988, Maybank Indonesia was permitted to operate as a foreign exchange bank. In addition, Maybank Indonesia joined the Indonesian Stock Exchange in the same year. Maybank Indonesia, one of the largest banks in Indonesia which is part of the Maybank Group and consists of regional and global networks, has 428 branches as of December 31 2016, including the largest sharia branch and micro-office in Indonesia. Additionally, Maybank has overseas locations in Mumbai, India, and Mauritius. Maybank also provides 19 mobile cash vehicles, 1,633 ATMs and cash deposit machines (CDM) which are connected to 3,500 Maybank ATMs in Malaysia and Singapore via the MEPS network, as well as 20,000 ATMs which are members of ATM Prima, ATM Bersama, CIRRUS connection, and ALTO.

Previous research explains that Maybank launched its sharia business operations in October 2010, and has created various creative services and solutions to answer customer needs and capture opportunities in the regional financial industry which continues to grow. PT Maybank Nusa International is the initial name of PT Bank Maybank Syariah Indonesia. Based on the Statement of Decisions of the Extraordinary General Meeting of Shareholders, Bank Maybank Syariah Indonesia will change its name and run its entire business in accordance with Islamic law. Based on the Decree of the Governor of Bank Indonesia No. 12, dated 23 September 2010, banks are permitted to change into commercial banks that carry out sharia-compliant business activities. On October 11, 2010, the Bank began carrying out Sharia commercial business.

Previous research explained that the main difference between conventional Maybank income and Maybank sharia is that conventional Maybank generates income by collecting interest from loans and investments, while Maybank sharia generates income through sharing profits with its customers in the form of shares. In the profit sharing system, Maybank Syariah works together with its customers to share profits resulting from transactions or investments carried out together. The resulting profits are shared based on a previous agreement, where customers will get a certain share of the profits generated. Sharia bank income is not subject to interest or usury, because sharia principles prohibit taking interest or usury in

financial transactions. Instead, Islamic banks generate income through profit sharing or fee-based income. In this case, Maybank sharia income comes from profits generated from investments and transactions with its customers, as well as fees charged to customers for the services provided.

Research regarding Bank Maybank Indonesia, Tbk has increased from year to year on the Garuda page (Digital Reference Garba) scientific publications regarding Bank Maybank from 2013 to 2022, there are 50 studies. Of this number, 47 studies discussed Conventional Maybank and 3 studies discussed Maybank Syariah. This research also includes research developments regarding Maybank Syariah. This research aims to ascertain the evolution of Maybank Sharia and Conventional over a nine year period, from 2013 to 2022, using the VOSviewer bibliometric method and literature analysis reviews.

B. Literature Review

PT BII Finance Center, which is now better known as PT Maybank Indonesia Finance (Maybank Finance), was established based on the Amendment to the Deed of Establishment (Juncto) No. 225 of 1959, which is an amendment to the Establishment Deed No. 163 dated 13 February 1959. Currently, Maybank has 555 locations, including 33 Maybank Finance locations and 356 Maybank Indonesia locations. In addition, there are 1,033 ATMs connected to more than 20,000 ATMs through the ATM PRIMA, ATM Bersama, ALTO and CIRRUS networks, as well as 3,500 Maybank ATMs in Malaysia, Singapore and Brunei.

The study of bibliographic analysis of scientific activities is called bibliometric analysis. Bibliometric studies are based on the idea that a researcher should conduct research and share findings with others. If researchers work together to explore a particular research problem, knowledge will develop and continue to grow as a result. Research undoubtedly requires data from the findings of previous scientific work carried out by other people. It is recommended to have publications to demonstrate production when applying traditional input-output models to describe scientific research processes. Articles and monographs, which are considered conclusive statements of research findings, constitute the majority of publications.

VOSViewer is a computer application used to create and display bibliometric records, allowing the creation and visualization of networks and relationships found in articles or publication extracts using text mining technology. By using this application, researchers can view publication maps in various ways, including zooming, scrolling, and using a search system (browsing), so they can map articles and publications in more depth.

The first and most important stage in creating a research plan is conducting a Library Research. It is possible to develop a specific topic or problem for a Library Research by reading various books, journals, and other sources related to the research topic. A Library Research is conducted to introduce new studies on a particular topic that practitioners of the field should pay attention to in their articles.

C. Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature studies reviews. The research object is Maybank Sharia and Conventional Banks. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Bank Maybank originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then searching for journal titles based on the title words category

with the keyword "Bank Maybank" over the entire year (2013-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on literature studies review.

D. Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Sharia and Conventional Bank Maybank

Based on the results of searching scientific publications about Maybank Sharia and Conventional Banks in the period 2013 to 2022, it can be seen that there has been an increase in the number of publications every year, especially in the last 5 years. 2021 will be the year with the highest number of publications, namely 10 publications. The publication data obtained was in the form of 47 article titles originating from accredited national journals. In 2021 there will be 10 article publications related to research on Bank Maybank. The average Maybank Bank scientific publication is around 5 articles per year.

Table 1. Publication data regarding Bank Maybank Syariah and Conventional

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2013	1	2018	6
2014	1	2019	6
2015	2	2020	5
2016	3	2021	10
2017	5	2022	8
Total 47			

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 2 shows the 8 institutions that publish the most articles about Maybank Bank. The International Journal of Science, Technology & Management is the institution that publishes the most journals about Bank Maybank, namely 4 articles.

Table 2. Affiliates/institutions publishing journals regarding Maybank Syariah and Conventional Banks

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
International Journal of Science, Technology & Management	4
Diponegoro Law Journal, Journal of Humanities, Social Science, Public Administration and Management (HUSOCPUMENT), Scientific Journal of Management and Business	3
TOURISM JOURNAL, EMBA Journal: Journal of Economic, Management, Business and Accounting Research, AGGREGATE JOURNAL, BUSINESS ECONOMICS	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 3 shows that Seru and Merselina from Tribhuwana Tunggal University are the researchers who wrote the most scientific journals about Maybank Sharia and Conventional Banks, namely 2 scientific publications. Sukeaesih and Imas from Syekh Yusuf Islamic University also succeeded in scientific publications twice.

Table 3. Researcher productivity regarding Maybank Sharia and Conventional Banks

Researcher	Number of Publications
Seru & Marselina, Sukaesih & Imas	2
Andrawati, Catharina Aprilia Hellyyani; Fatchur Rohman, Aprilianti Erika, Astiti Chandra; Amelia, Ardani, Devita Heriana Putri; I Gusti Ayu Gangga Santi Dewi, Barizki, Rezzi Nanda, Belle Risca Junia, Siti Mahmuda, Budiharto, Dera Apriliyanto Putra, Devina Janice, Aminah, Rinitami Njatrijani, Dewi, Maria Evania, Dwi Wahyuni, Nigstayumd Mona, Jamiatul Khair NIM, Ferdian, Melitina Tecolalu; Hery Winoto Tj; Ferdian, Fernandes, Sapparso; Melitina Tecolalu, Hadijah, Moch Benny Alexandri; Meita Pragiwani; Siti, Hasanudin, Fergal Ramadhan Guskar; Moch Bukhori Muslim, Heryatno, Vina Andita Pratiwi; Elly Herawati; Probo, Islamiah, Deden; Sugianto; Darmin, Loisa, Vella Stephanie, Riris, Mahadi, Nur Nuha Binti Nor Hisam, Daisy Mui Hung Kee, Naibaho, Maurits Sipatuhtar, Charles V Slanipar; Raston Sitio, Nangoi Rudy J, Watung, Mercy Natalia, Grace B; Pusung, Nurhidayanti, Lely Awintasari; Maulida, Nurroshidah, Siti, Permatasari, Dwi Novita cahyaningtyas, Pratiwi, Amelia Niken, Purnama, Steven; Eka Desy, Rabbani, Candra Wijayangka; Budi Rustandi Kartawinata; Muhammad, Ramli, Fahriansyah, Santoso, Soegoeng Wahyudi, Budi Haryono, Ricky Hertanu, Soebroto, Alma Aprilia; Nina Woelan, Sofyan, Widya N Rosari; Dinda Estasari; Tito, Sorongan, Marselly, Sulaeman, Eman, Sutanto, Widya Erdina Sandra; Sufian Martyr; Himawan Arif, Teguh, Naomi Malinda, Wahyoedi, Jimmy Yosol; PM Budi Haryono; Soegeng, Maduma Sormin, Winata, Andi Ahmad Gunadi; Benny Ismail Sigarlaki; Widia, Yogatama, Evita Frisdiana, Jaya Wardani; Titi Nur Vidyarini; Astri, Yudena I Gusti Agung; Pascarani, Nyoman Dewi, Aulia Bunga.	1

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Maybank Sharia and Conventional Banks

These results were obtained from searches on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) which were exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then entered and analyzed using software VOSviewer. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding Maybank Sharia and Conventional Banks

Source: Data processed, VOSViewer 1.6.18 software

the network visualization on the co-wor map of research developments regarding Maybank Sharia and Conventional banks are divided into 7 classes consisting of 139 topics, as follows :

- Cluster 1. The red color consists of 32 topics, namely : activity, acquisition, bank, bank maybank, bank maybank Indonesia, bii maybank, capital, condition, difference, earnings, financial institutions, financial performance, Good Corporate Governance (GCG), interest, Indonesian Rupiah (IDR), liquidity ratio, maybank syariah, maybank syariah bank, period, pre, profit sharing, pt bank maybank indonesia, pt bank maybank indonesia tbk, ratio, research method, rgec, risk profile, secondary data, sound level, tbk.
- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 23 topics, namely : analysis, BII Maybank Malang Branch, brand awareness, cashless payment, customer, customer loyalty, customer sacrifice, customer satisfaction, development, event, factor, impact, Maybank, Maybank Bali Marathon, pandemic, product, research, respondent, sales person, service, significant impact, vehicle.
- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 20 topics, namely : brand image, company, country, customer loyalty of BII Maybank customers, data analysis, decision, good service quality, intention, Maybank finance customer respondents, price, price perception, promotion, PT Maybank Indonesian finance, purchasing decision, researcher, role, service quality, significant effect, significant influence, case study.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 20 topics, namely : addition, agreement, buyer, car hire purchase, consumer, credit, exporter, government, importer, installment, Letter of Credit (LC), law, legal audit, maybank finance, regulations Financial Services Authority (POJK), property, purchase, regulation, seller.
- Cluster 5. The color purple consists of 17 topics, namely : bank maybank indonesia tbk, bank maybank Medan branch, employee performance, employee performance, leadership communication style, maybank unit, performance, population, positive influence, questionnaire, relationship, sample, study, trust, variable.

- Cluster 6. The light blue color consists of 16 topics, namely : assets, Operating Costs and Operating Income (BOPO), Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Earning Per Share (EPS), equity, long term, data analysis methods, Non Performing Financing (NPF), population, return, Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), shares, short term.
- Cluster 7. The orange color consists of 11 topics, namely : car buying decision, consumer purchasing decision, credit procedure, effect, influence, integrated marketing communication, interest rate, perception, purchase intention, purchase interest.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Maybank Sharia and Conventional Bank Products

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 3 Maybank Sharia and Conventional Bank products, namely:

First, vehicle credit. Maybank Bank offers various types of vehicle credit products that can be tailored to customer needs and financial capabilities. Several vehicle credit products offered by Bank Maybank include: (1) Maybank New Car: This product makes it possible to buy a new car with easy installments and a term of up to 5 years, and can get competitive interest rates and financing of up to 80% of car price; (2) Maybank Used Cars: This product makes it possible to buy used cars with flexible installments and terms of up to 4 years, and can get financing up to 80% of the used car price and competitive interest rates; (3) Maybank New Motorbike: This product makes it possible to buy a new motorbike with affordable installments and a term of up to 4 years, and can get financing up to 80% of the price of the new motorbike and competitive interest rates; (4) Maybank Used Motorbike: This product makes it possible to buy a used motorbike with low installments and a term of up to 3 years, and can get financing up to 70% of the price of the used motorbike and at competitive interest rates. Apart from that, Bank Maybank also offers several additional features and benefits such as vehicle insurance, interest reduction if you make early payments, and flexible installment determination according to the customer's financial capabilities.

Second, Letters of Credit. LC is a payment guarantee from the bank to the exporter, which is issued at the request and instructions of the importer. The following are the steps for using LC products at Maybank: (1) The importer requests to open an LC from Maybank. This request should include transaction details, including payment amount, shipping instructions, and required documents. (2) Maybank will carry out credit evaluations for importers, including checking credit worthiness and ability to pay. If the requirements are met, Maybank will issue an LC. (3) LC issued by Maybank will be sent to the exporter via a different bank (correspondent bank) in the exporter's country. (4) The exporter will deliver the goods according to the instructions stated in the LC. Exporters must also prepare the documents requested in the LC, such as invoices, certificates of origin and other shipping documentation. (5) The exporter sends these documents to the correspondent bank, which will then forward them to Maybank. (6) Maybank will check the documents received, and if everything complies with the LC requirements, Maybank will pay the exporter according to the value stated in the LC. When using the Letter of Credit product at Maybank, there are certain costs that must be paid by the importer, such as administration fees, LC delivery fees, correspondent bank commission fees, and other fees related to international trade transactions.

Third, mortgage restructuring. This mortgage restructuring aims to help customers maintain home ownership and avoid late payments or even default. There are several things that need to be considered regarding the KPR Restructuring product at Bank Maybank, including: (1) KPR Restructuring Requirements: Customers who wish to apply for the KPR Restructuring program at Bank Maybank must fulfill several conditions, such as having a good credit record and not being in default status., have paid off the mortgage installments for at least 12 months, and

have the ability to pay the restructured mortgage installments. (2) Types of KPR Restructuring: Bank Maybank offers several types of KPR restructuring, such as extending the credit term, changing interest rates, reducing installments, or a combination of several of these options. (3) Application Process: To apply for the KPR Restructuring program, customers must fill out the application form and attach supporting documents such as KTP, NPWP, income statement and home ownership documents. After that, customers will be contacted by Maybank Bank officers to discuss available restructuring options. (4) KPR Restructuring Fees: Bank Maybank makes it easy for customers who apply for the KPR Restructuring program by not charging additional fees or fines for changes to payment schedules or interest rates. (5) Impact of KPR Restructuring: KPR restructuring can have a positive impact on customers, such as reducing the burden of mortgage installments and maintaining home ownership. However, keep in mind that changes in payment schedules or interest rates can affect the number of installments and interest that must be paid in the long term. Therefore, before applying for the KPR Restructuring program, customers are advised to carefully consider their financial capabilities and long-term needs.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Performance of Maybank Sharia and Conventional Banks

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 11 regarding the performance of Maybank Sharia and Conventional Banks, namely:

First, acquisition. Acquisitions can affect Maybank's bank performance in several ways. First, acquisitions can help banks expand their business and gain access to new markets. This can increase a bank's revenue and profits and positively influence its performance. Second, acquisitions can provide scale benefits, which can help banks lower costs and increase efficiency. With economies of scale, banks can reduce costs, increase efficiency and increase profitability. However, acquisitions also have risks. Unsuccessful acquisitions can have a negative impact on bank performance. If the acquisition is carried out at high costs or does not achieve the expected profits, this can cause significant losses for the bank. Additionally, integration of an acquired bank can be challenging, especially if the culture and management systems of the acquired bank are different from those of the acquiring bank. If integration is not done well, it can affect the bank's performance negatively.

Second, Non Performing Financing /NPF. The effect of NPF on Maybank bank performance can be explained as follows: (1) Decreased profitability: NPF can affect Maybank bank profitability because the bank has to bear higher costs to resolve bad financing. These costs include asset expropriation costs, court costs, attorney fees and other costs. This can reduce bank profits and impact overall financial performance. (2) Decreased liquidity: NPF can affect Maybank's bank liquidity because bad financing can limit the bank's ability to channel funds to potentially profitable sectors. This can affect the bank's ability to meet its liquidity needs and worsen financial performance. (3) Decreased credibility: NPF can affect Maybank's credibility in the eyes of the public because poor financial performance can reduce customer and investor confidence in the bank. This can affect the bank's reputation and reduce the potential for future business growth.

Third, Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR. CAR is expressed as a percentage and is calculated by comparing the bank's capital with the number of assets it owns. The higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to bear risk and the safer the bank. In the context of Maybank bank, a high CAR can have a positive influence on its performance. Some of the influences that can occur include: (1) Ability to obtain additional capital: Banks that have a high CAR will find it easier to obtain additional capital from investors or other financial institutions. This can help banks to expand their operations and provide better services to customers. (2) Ability to expand

business: In a competitive business environment, banks that have a high CAR will find it easier to expand their business. Banks can offer more diverse products and services to customers, such as credit and deposits with more competitive interest rates. (3) Ability to overcome risks: In its operations, banks always face risks that must be overcome. Banks that have a high CAR will find it easier to overcome these risks, such as credit risk, liquidity risk and market risk. This will make the bank more stable and able to face uncertain economic situations. However, on the other hand, a CAR that is too high can also have a negative impact on bank performance. If a bank focuses too much on raising capital and does not expand its business, it can miss opportunities to grow and develop.

Fourth, Operating Expenses Operating Income/BOPO. The higher the BOPO, the higher the operational costs incurred by the bank to generate operational income, so it can have a negative impact on bank performance. The influence of BOPO on Maybank bank performance can be seen from several factors, including: (1) Profitability: The higher the BOPO, the lower the bank's profitability level. This is because the higher the operational costs incurred by banks to generate operational income, the more difficult it is for banks to achieve high profits. (2) Efficiency: A low BOPO indicates better efficiency in managing operational costs. In this way, banks can maximize income from the same or lower operating income, thereby increasing bank operational efficiency. (3) Competitiveness: Low BOPO can help banks increase their competitiveness in the market. Banks can offer more competitive products and services at lower costs, thereby attracting more customers and increasing market share.

Fifth, Net Rewards. The influence of Net Rewards on Bank Maybank's performance can be seen from several points of view, as follows: (1) Income: If Bank Maybank's Net Rewards increase, then the bank's income will also increase. This can improve the bank's financial performance, such as increasing net profit. (2) Customer Satisfaction: If the bank is able to offer products with low interest or offer competitive interest, then customers will be more satisfied and more likely to remain bank customers. In the long term, this can improve bank performance, such as increasing deposit and credit volumes. (3) Cost Efficiency: If Bank Maybank can maintain low interest on funding sources, the bank can reduce borrowing costs and increase cost efficiency. This will allow banks to earn greater profits from each transaction. (4) Risk: Although Net Rewards can increase a bank's income, it can also increase the risks faced by the bank. For example, if Bank Maybank offers products with interest that is too low or disburses credit that is too high, the bank may experience credit risk or liquidity risk.

Sixth, Return On Assets / ROA. The higher the ROA, the more efficient the bank is in generating profits from its assets. ROA is also used as an indicator of bank financial performance. The influence of ROA on Bank Maybank's performance can be explained as follows: (1) Showing good financial performance: The higher the ROA, the better the financial performance of Bank Maybank. A high ROA shows that Maybank Bank is able to generate good profits from its assets. (2) Strengthening customer trust: A high ROA can also strengthen customer trust in Maybank Bank. Customers will have more confidence in placing their funds in Maybank Bank if the bank has a high ROA, because this shows that the bank is able to generate good and stable profits. (3) Increasing competitiveness: A high ROA can also increase Bank Maybank's competitiveness in the market. In a tight competitive environment, banks that are able to generate high ROA will be more attractive to investors and customers.

Seventh, Return On Equity /ROE. The higher a company's ROE, the more efficient the company is in using equity to generate profits. In the case of Bank Maybank, the influence of ROE on bank performance can be seen as follows: (1) Shows the efficiency of using equity: The higher the ROE of Bank Maybank, the more efficient the use of bank equity in generating profits. This shows that banks can generate more profits with less investment, which is a good indicator of financial

performance. (2) Increase investor confidence: A high ROE can increase investor confidence in Maybank Bank's financial performance. This can result in increased share prices and investor interest, which in turn can provide access to better funding sources. (3) Influence on dividend policy: A high ROE can give Bank Maybank the ability to pay larger dividends to shareholders. This can increase the investment attractiveness of banks and improve long-term financial performance.

Eighth, Liquidity Ratio. In general, the higher a bank's liquidity ratio, the better the bank's ability to meet its short-term obligations. However, too high a liquidity ratio can also indicate that the bank is not utilizing its assets effectively to generate optimal income. In terms of bank performance, the liquidity ratio can influence bank performance in several ways, including: (1) The bank's ability to fulfill short-term obligations: A high liquidity ratio indicates that the bank can fulfill its short-term obligations smoothly, so the bank will not experience problems liquidity and can maintain credibility in the market. (2) Asset use efficiency: A liquidity ratio that is too high can indicate that the bank is not using its assets effectively to generate income, which can affect the bank's profitability. (3) The bank's ability to provide loans: A liquidity ratio that is too low can indicate that the bank does not have sufficient funds to provide loans to customers, which can affect the bank's business growth.

Ninth, operational efficiency. Operational efficiency can have a significant influence on Bank Maybank's performance. Operating efficiency refers to a bank's ability to utilize available resources effectively and efficiently to generate revenue. Several ways in which operational efficiency can influence Bank Maybank's performance, include: (1) Increasing profitability: With good operational efficiency, Bank Maybank can reduce operational costs and increase profit margins. This can increase a bank's profitability and make it more attractive to investors. (2) Increase customer satisfaction: Good operational efficiency can also help Bank Maybank provide better service to customers, including faster response times and lower error rates. This can increase customer satisfaction and strengthen the bank's image. (3) Increasing competitiveness: With good operational efficiency, Bank Maybank can offer more competitive products and services at lower costs. This can help the bank compete with other banks in the market. (4) Reduce risk: Good operational efficiency can also help Maybank Bank manage operational risks better. With a more efficient system, banks can minimize the risk of human error and reduce the potential for fraud.

Tenth, Solvency Ratio. Solvency Ratio is a financial ratio that measures a bank's ability to fulfill its long-term financial obligations, including obligations to customers, investors and other related parties. The solvency ratio that is commonly used is the capital adequacy ratio (CAR). A fairly high increase in the solvency ratio can demonstrate the bank's ability to manage credit risk and other risks effectively, as well as providing confidence to investors and customers. This can improve the bank's reputation and also facilitate bank access to obtain funds from the capital market. In the context of Maybank, increasing the solvency ratio can have a positive impact on bank performance. Maybank Bank is one of the largest banks in Southeast Asia, and has a fairly strong position in the Indonesian market. Increasing the solvency ratio can help banks obtain funds from the capital market at lower costs, thereby increasing bank profits. However, an excessive increase in the solvency ratio can also have a negative impact on bank performance. If a bank maintains a capital level that is too high, this can limit the bank's ability to generate optimal profits. Therefore, banks need to find a balance between sufficient capital levels to meet regulatory requirements and also maintain the bank's ability to generate optimal profits.

Eleventh, the Covid-19 pandemic. The Covid-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on the banking industry, including the performance of Bank Maybank. Some possible impacts include: (1) Decline in financial performance: The Covid-19 pandemic has affected the financial performance of Maybank Bank like

other banks. The lockdown and social restrictions caused a decline in economic activity which had an impact on bank financial performance. Maybank Bank may also experience an increase in credit risk costs due to the possibility of an increase in non-performing loans due to the difficult economic situation. (2) Decreased operational performance: The Covid-19 pandemic may also have an impact on Bank Maybank's operational performance. Banks may experience difficulties in carrying out their operations due to social restrictions and lockdowns, which have an impact on reducing the number of employees working in the office. Apart from that, this pandemic has also changed people's consumption patterns, with consumers switching from physical banking services to digital banking services. As a result, Bank Maybank had to change its operating strategy to adapt to these changes. (3) Changes in consumer behavior: The Covid-19 pandemic can also change consumer behavior towards banking products and services. Some products and services that consumers are typically interested in may no longer meet their needs due to the pandemic. This can affect Bank Maybank's performance and require better business strategy adjustments.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Determinants of Maybank Sharia and Conventional Bank Employee Work Motivation

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 6 determinants of work motivation for Maybank Sharia and Conventional Bank employees, namely:

First, employee benefits use PSAK 24. PSAK 24 helps banks to provide accurate and transparent financial reports regarding employee reward programs. With PSAK 24, Maybank employees can know clearly and transparently about their reward program, so they feel appreciated and motivated to work harder. This can improve employee performance at Bank Maybank.

Second, competence. The ability and expertise of employees in carrying out their tasks greatly influences their performance. Employees who have good competencies will be more effective and efficient at work. Bank Maybank can improve employee performance by providing appropriate training and development to increase employee competency.

Third, work environment. A positive and supportive work environment can improve employee performance. Employees who feel comfortable and appreciated at work will be more motivated to work hard and achieve organizational goals. Maybank Bank can create a positive work environment by providing the support and facilities needed by employees, as well as paying attention to their welfare.

Fourth, motivation. Motivated employees will work harder and achieve organizational goals more effectively. Maybank Bank can increase employee motivation by providing fair rewards and recognition for their achievements.

Fifth, rewards. Rewards or appreciation for employee achievements can also improve their performance. Employees who feel appreciated and recognized for their achievements will be more motivated to work hard and achieve organizational goals. Maybank Bank can provide appropriate and fair rewards for employees who achieve targets and achieve organizational goals.

Sixth, organizational climate. Organizational climate is employees' perceptions regarding organizational culture, values and norms that exist in the workplace. A positive organizational climate can improve employee performance. Maybank Bank can create a positive organizational climate by fostering an inclusive, collaborative and supportive work culture.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Determinants of Customer Interest and Satisfaction in Transactions at Maybank Sharia and Conventional Banks

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 16 regarding the determinants of customer interest and satisfaction in transactions at Bank Maybank Syariah and Conventional, namely:

First, organizational culture. Organizational culture can influence customers' interest in making transactions at Bank Maybank. If Bank Maybank has a positive organizational culture, such as being open, transparent and responsive to customer needs, then this can increase customer trust and motivate them to choose Bank Maybank as their choice for transactions.

Second, service quality. Service quality is also an important factor in influencing customer interest in making transactions at Bank Maybank. Customers need good, fast and effective service. If Bank Maybank can provide good quality service, then this can make customers feel comfortable and happy using Bank Maybank's services.

Third, communication patterns. Good communication patterns can strengthen the relationship between Maybank Bank and customers. Maybank Bank needs to have a clear and open communication pattern with customers. This can help increase trust and build good relationships with customers.

Fourth, customer sacrifice. Customer sacrifices can also influence customers' interest in making transactions at Bank Maybank. If customers feel that they have to pay high fees or make other sacrifices to use Maybank Bank services, then this can reduce their interest in making transactions at Maybank Bank.

Fifth, work competency. Work competency is an important factor in determining the quality of services provided by Bank Maybank. If Bank Maybank has staff who are skilled and competent in providing services to customers, then this can increase customer interest in using Bank Maybank services.

Sixth, brand image through online media. A positive brand image can influence customer interest in making transactions at Bank Maybank. Online media such as websites, social media and online advertising can help banks build a strong brand image and attract customer interest.

Seventh, product. The products offered by Bank Maybank can influence customers' interest in making transactions at this bank. If the products offered are in line with customer needs and preferences, then customer interest in making transactions at this bank will increase.

Eighth, Brand Awareness. The level of awareness or Brand Awareness of Bank Maybank will influence customers' interest in making transactions at this bank. The higher the level of customer awareness of the Maybank brand, the more likely they are to make transactions at this bank.

Ninth, promotion. Promotions carried out by Bank Maybank can influence customers' interest in making transactions at this bank. Promotions such as discounts, cashback and other attractive offers can increase customer interest in using Maybank Bank products and services.

Tenth, interest rates. The interest rates offered by Bank Maybank can influence customers' interest in making transactions at this bank. Competitive and attractive interest rates can be an important factor for customers in choosing a bank for transactions.

Eleventh, credit procedures. Customers are interested in making transactions with Bank Maybank because the credit procedures are easy and fast. Banks that have easy and structured credit procedures can help customers get the funds they need quickly and efficiently.

Twelfth, profit sharing. Customers tend to be attracted to banks that offer high profit sharing. Maybank Bank has a competitive and attractive profit sharing program for customers to save and invest their money.

Thirteenth, pricing policy. A fair and competitive pricing policy is very important in attracting customer interest. Maybank Bank offers products and services at reasonable and competitive prices.

Fourteenth, property attributes. Property attributes, such as location and amenities, also play a role in attracting customer interest. Bank Maybank has a strategic location and adequate facilities to meet customer needs.

Fifteenth, marketing. Effective marketing activities also have an influence in attracting customer interest. Maybank Bank carries out various effective marketing and promotional activities to attract customer interest.

Sixteenth, salesperson. Salespeople who are skilled and knowledgeable about the bank's products and services also play an important role in attracting customer interest. Maybank Bank has a well-trained and experienced sales team to provide the right and best financial solutions for customers.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Innovation at Maybank Sharia and Conventional Banks

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 2 regarding innovations at Maybank Sharia and Conventional Banks, namely:

First, the service talent internship program through mini bank activities. This is a program that aims to provide work experience and practical skills to apprentices in the banking industry. The following are the steps to take part in the Talenta Service internship program through Bank Mini activities at Bank Maybank: (1) Requirements: Make sure that you meet the requirements set by Bank Maybank for the Talenta Service internship program. General requirements usually include final semester students or recent graduates with a minimum GPA of 3.0, good English language skills, and an interest in banking and customer service. (2) Registration: Register as a Talent Service apprentice through Bank Mini activities at Bank Maybank. You can find information regarding this registration via the official Maybank Bank website or through the nearest branch office. (3) Selection: After registering, you will undergo a selection process which usually consists of several stages, such as a written test, interview and skills test. If you pass the selection, you will be given the opportunity to take part in the Talent Service internship program. (4) Internship Program: The Talenta Service internship program usually lasts for several months. During this period, you will be placed in different business units at Maybank Bank, such as Teller, Customer Service, or Personal Banker. You will learn about the duties and responsibilities in each business unit, as well as practice the practical skills needed in the banking industry. (5) Evaluation: During the internship program, you will be evaluated regularly by your superior or supervisor. This evaluation will help you improve your performance and skills, and prepare you to work in the banking industry after the internship program is completed. (6) Certificate: After completing the internship program, you will be given a certificate as proof that you have completed the Talent Service internship program at Bank Maybank. This certificate can be an added value in your future career.

Second, the Maybank Bali Marathon 2017 integrated marketing communication strategy through Sport Motivational. To promote the 2017 Maybank Bali Marathon through Sport Motivational, several integrated marketing communication strategies can be implemented, including: (1) Creating a Story-Based Campaign (Storytelling). Creating a story about the runners' journey in achieving their target at the 2017 Maybank Bali Marathon could be an interesting campaign. This story can be taken from the runner's experiences, training, preparation, and the challenges they face. This story can be presented in the form of a short video, photo or article which can be shared on social media or the official Maybank Bali Marathon website. (2) Using Inspirational Content. Creating inspirational content such as quotes and motivational sentences can help increase the enthusiasm of runners and prospective runners. This content can be used as marketing material and shared on social media, official websites and publications related to the Maybank Bali Marathon. This can help build runners' sense of

involvement and loyalty towards the Maybank Bali Marathon. (3) Using Influencers. Using influencers related to running or marathon sports can help expand the marketing reach of the Maybank Bali Marathon 2017. Influencers can be professional runners, coaches or motivators who have large followers on social media. Influencers can post content about the 2017 Maybank Bali Marathon and provide tips or suggestions on how to face challenges in the race. (4) Using the Live Streaming Feature. Maybank Bali Marathon 2017 can add a live streaming feature to social media or the official website. This feature can help fans and runners who cannot come to the race location to stay involved in race activities. This can help increase runners' involvement and loyalty to the Maybank Bali Marathon. (5) Using Digital Advertising. Using digital advertising such as Google Adwords advertising or advertising on social media can help increase the marketing reach of the Maybank Bali Marathon 2017. Advertisements can be created with a specific target audience and attract the interest of runners and sports fans. Advertisements can be directed to the official Maybank Bali Marathon website or registration site.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Problems at Maybank Sharia and Conventional Banks

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 5 regarding problems at Maybank Sharia and Conventional Banks, namely:

First, the law on guaranteeing electronic mortgage rights in Law no. 4 of 1996. In the event that Maybank provides loans with electronic mortgage collateral, the bank must comply with the provisions stipulated in Law no. 4 of 1996. Several provisions that must be complied with are: (1) Registration of electronic mortgage rights must be carried out at the local Land Office and announced in the State Gazette. (2) Registration of electronic mortgage rights must use valid electronic means and meet the requirements set by the government. (3) Electronic mortgage rights can only be granted for goods that can be transferred electronically. (4) Bank Maybank must pay attention to the principle of prudence in providing loans with electronic mortgage collateral. The bank must ensure that the collateral object provided by the debtor meets the requirements and has sufficient value as collateral. (5) If a default occurs by the debtor, Maybank bank has the right to execute the collateral object secured by electronic mortgage rights. (6) The granting of electronic mortgage rights must be carried out by means of a notarial deed.

Second, legal protection for Safe Deposit Box rental agreements. The Safe Deposit Box rental agreement with Bank Maybank is regulated by agreement law and also regulations issued by Bank Indonesia and Bank Maybank itself. As the renting party, you must understand and agree to all terms and conditions related to the Safe Deposit Box rental agreement, which are usually stated in the contract agreed to by both parties. Several things that need to be considered in the Safe Deposit Box rental agreement with Maybank Bank include: (1) Rental period: Usually Maybank Bank offers various Safe Deposit Box rental periods, such as 1 year, 3 years, 5 years or more. The renting party must understand and agree to the time period offered and the related conditions. (2) Rental fees: Bank Maybank will set a Safe Deposit Box rental fee, which can vary depending on the size of the box chosen and the rental period. These fees may also change from time to time. Make sure you understand the rental fees associated with the Safe Deposit Box rental agreement. (3) Renter's obligations: The renting party must comply with all terms and conditions in the Safe Deposit Box rental agreement, such as not giving the box key to another party without approval from Maybank Bank, and handing over the box key to Maybank Bank when the rental period ends.. The renting party must also pay the rental fee on time. (4) Maybank Bank's responsibility: Maybank Bank is responsible for maintaining the security of the Safe Deposit Box and ensuring that only the owner has access to the box. Maybank Bank must also provide

insurance protection against the risk of loss or damage to objects stored in the Safe Deposit Box.

Third, the difference between conventional bank revenue and profit sharing from sharia banks. The main difference between conventional Maybank income and Maybank sharia is that conventional Maybank generates income by collecting interest from loans and investments, while Maybank sharia generates income through sharing profits with its customers in the form of profit sharing. In the profit sharing system, Maybank Syariah works together with its customers to share profits resulting from transactions or investments carried out together. The profits generated are divided based on previous agreements, where customers will get a certain share of the profits generated. Sharia bank income is not subject to interest or usury, because sharia principles prohibit taking interest or usury in financial transactions. Instead, Islamic banks generate income through profit sharing or fee-based income. In this case, Maybank sharia income comes from profits generated from investments and transactions with its customers, as well as fees charged to customers for the services provided.

Fourth, liability for customer losses when using fund savings services. Banks have a responsibility to ensure that customer funds stored in them are safe and protected from loss or theft. Banks must comply with applicable rules and regulations in the banking industry, including following strict security procedures and protecting customers' personal information. If there is a loss in customer funds stored at Bank Maybank, the customer has the right to submit a claim and request compensation from Bank Maybank. However, this depends on the cause of the loss and whether Maybank Bank is responsible for the loss. If the customer can prove that the loss they experienced was caused by Maybank Bank's error or negligence, then Maybank Bank will be responsible and must pay compensation according to the loss experienced by the customer. However, if the loss occurs due to the customer's error or negligence, then Maybank Bank is not responsible for the loss. Therefore, it is very important for customers to understand and comply with security procedures and the use of fund storage services at Maybank Bank, as well as maintaining the security of their personal information.

Fifth, performance evaluation using the RGEC method. The RGEC (Risk, Governance, Ethics, and Compliance) method is a framework for evaluating a company's performance which includes four dimensions, namely risk, governance, ethics and compliance. To apply the RGEC method to Bank Maybank, the following steps can be taken: (1) Risk: It is necessary to evaluate the risks at Bank Maybank. This risk evaluation includes risk identification, risk analysis, and determining risk mitigation. At Maybank Bank, risks that need to be evaluated include credit risk, market risk, operational risk and liquidity risk. Risk evaluation can be done by examining Maybank Bank's financial records, risk reports and internal risk evaluation. (2) Governance: Governance evaluation needs to be carried out at Bank Maybank. This evaluation covers how Maybank Bank is managed, including management policies, supervision and implementation of banking standards. Governance evaluation can be carried out by examining management documents, organizational structure and supervisory mechanisms at Bank Maybank. (3) Ethics: An ethical evaluation is carried out to evaluate how Maybank Bank treats customers, employees and shareholders. This evaluation includes the development of a strong ethical culture, anti-corruption policies, and the actions taken by Bank Maybank in dealing with ethical issues. Ethical evaluation can be carried out by examining Maybank Bank's ethical policies, reporting ethical violations, and employee experience at Maybank Bank. (4) Compliance: Compliance evaluation needs to be carried out at Bank Maybank. This evaluation includes an assessment of Bank Maybank's compliance with applicable regulations and laws. Compliance evaluation can be carried out by examining compliance documents, internal and external audits, as well as actions taken by Bank Maybank in handling compliance violations.

E. Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- Number of research publications around Maybank Sharia and Conventional during the period 2013 to 2022, shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 47 research articles, which come from national journals indexed by Sinta.
- The affiliate/institution that publishes the most research results is the International Journal of Science, Technology & Management, with 4 articles.
- The researchers who were most productive in publishing research results were Seru and Merselina from Tribhuwana Tunggal University, namely 2 scientific publications. Sukesaesih and Imas from Syekh Yusuf Islamic University also succeeded in scientific publications twice.
- In the mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments regarding Maybank Syariah and Conventional are divided into 7 clusters and 139 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 32 topics, cluster 2 consists of 23 topics, cluster 3 consists of 20 topics, cluster 4 consists of 20 topics, cluster 5 consists of 17 topics, and cluster 6 consists of 16 topics, and cluster 7 consists of 11 topics..
- Based on the Library Research, there are 3 main research themes, namely : (1) Product; (2) Financial performance; (3) Determinants of employee work motivation; (4) Determinants of customer interest and satisfaction in transactions; (5) Innovation; and (6) Other problems with the company.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- the Library Research study can be explained in a more complex way.

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